

Comparative Microbial Evaluation of Salted and Frozen Fish Sold in Faisalabad

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SUMMARY

The primary aim was to evaluate the microbial composition of frozen and salted fish samples collected from district Faisalabad. For the purpose of study, three fish species, namely Rohu, Sardine and Tuna were selected to conduct microbial evaluations of both salted and frozen fish samples. These evaluations were then compared with microbial counts obtained from marketed samples. Salted fish are fish covered with dry salt and thus preserved for later eating, such as canned Tuna and Sardines while frozen fish products are packaged to minimize dehydration and oxidation. The number and variety of microbes associated with fish are influenced by the geographical place, the season and the harvest procedure. For the sake of understanding the microbial status of frozen and salted fish samples, bacterial culturing technique was used using nutrient agar media. Total viable count was estimated. Quantitative results after microbial count was subjected to graphical analyses using Minitab software. The results indicated that the microbial count of salted and frozen fish samples was lower than that of the marketed samples. This suggested that the salted and frozen fish may have undergone some processes or conditions that inhibit the microbial growth more effectively as compared to the marketed fish.

Keywords: Salted fish, Frozen fish, Rohu, Sardine, Tuna, Nutrient Agar

INTRODUCTION

Aquaculture is the practice of farming aquatic organisms, such as fish, crustaceans, mollusks and aquatic plants in controlled environments. In response to high demand for fish products aquaculture production is increasing, expanding its share of total fish production to ensure a stable supply (Ntsama *et al.*, 2018).

Fish serves as vital source of biological molecules including omega-3 fatty acids, digestible proteins and fat soluble vitamins (like vitamin E and D) (Weichselbaum *et al.*, 2013). These compounds are vital in the human diet and play a positive role in preventing various diseases. The growing nutritional value and required nutrients found in fish have contributed to a gradual increase in public demand for fish and fish products in recent decades (Aubourg, 2018).

The Greek word for "life" bios, is where the phrase "microbiota" originates (Matei *et al.*, 2020). The assessment of microbiological quality entails the determining whether pathogenic bacteria are present and evaluating the sterility of fish (Gutema and Hailemichael, in 2021). Aerobic spore-forming bacteria can cause chemical and physical changes as well as microbiological degradation, which lowers the quality of

fish (Jalal *et al.*, 2017). However, microbial growth, endogenous enzyme activity, lipid 3 and protein oxidation and other variables all contribute to fish products losing their quality (Cropotova *et al.*, 2019).

Traditional salted fish reflects a significant nexus between human culinary traditions and biology. The osmotic principle, which states that water is drawn out of fish cells through osmosis because of the extraordinary absorption of salt in the surrounding environment, is the basis for the preservation method (Svanberg and Locker, 2020).

The primary purpose of salting is to partially replace the water that is removed from fish flesh with salt. Fish that have been salted have less water activity, which results in less microbial and enzymatic activity. (Liu *et al.*, 2021). Impacts of salting and curing on the structure of protein have also been associated to enzymatic movement, that is changed however not removed for the period of brine salting (Van Nguyen *et al.*, 2011).

Some species are more suited for salting because of anatomical and the physiological characteristics, like a higher oil content and resilience to the preventative process (Chacha *et al.*, 2021). Dried fish that has been salted or cured is a significant source of affordable animal protein for the general public, particularly for those living near the ocean. In India, the consumption of dried fish accounts for around 32% of all marine landings, with fresh fish consumption coming in second. Ordinary salt is used to kill osmophilic fungi as well as non-halophilic bacteria that generate spores (Sivaraman and Sivam, 2015).

Frozen fish has an impact on microorganisms. Moreover, organic appearances like oxidative rancidity, lipid and fat breakdown and protein changes are impacted by freezing (Gonçalves *et al.*, 2012). Freeze chilling food while it's being processed can have advantages for customers and businesses alike. When done properly, it can increase the economic value, decrease waste and prolong the shelf life of products. (Svendsen *et al.*, 2022). Freezing slows down the spoiling and deterioration process, but it also damages the tissue mechanically when ice crystals form (He *et al.*, 2024).

Freezing lowers storage temperatures and immobilizes liquid water, it is widely acknowledged as the most popular method for long-term food preservation because it slows down the rate at which food quality deteriorates. However, by volumetric expansion, ice crystallization during freezing will result in irreversible micro-structural damage to the food matrix and this disruptive alteration lowers the consumer's impression of overall quality of the meal (Kang *et al.*, 2020).

Existing studies have explored fish preservation and safety but they often neglect District Faisalabad unique environmental and sociocultural factors. These studies primarily focus on different regions and lack specificity to this locale. Moreover, while some recent research has investigated innovative preservation techniques and microbial aspects like umami peptide production, predominant bacteria during the curing process, but its applicability to the local context remains uncertain comprehensive study to ensure food safety and product quality in this specific region. To assess the impact of freezing and salting processes on microbial levels in fish. To analyze the effect of storage conditions on microbial growth.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Place of Experiment

The present research was accomplished at Fisheries Research Farm located at the Department of Zoology, Wildlife and Fisheries, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad.

Investigational species

- Rohu (*Labeo rohita*)
- Sardine (*Sardina pilchardus*)
- Tuna (*Thunnus*)

Sampling

Frozen and salted Rohu, Tuna and Sardines were taken from Metro mall, Imtiaz Super Market and Bambino Departmental Store. Samples were taken from the flesh and skin.

Apparatus and Chemicals

The following apparatus was required for microbiological research work. Glass slides, glass rod, spreader, cover slip, oven, distilled water, 100ml flask, matchbox, cotton plugs, NA media, ethanol, measuring cylinders, Eppendorf tubes, saline solution, micropipette tips of 100-1000 μ m, pH meter, DO and salinity meter, syringes, centrifuge tube.

Preparation of Culture Media

The culture media was prepared using a solution made with distilled water, which were then be placed in an autoclave and maintained at 15°C for about 20 minutes. The chemicals used in the laboratory are of high-quality measures and taken in standard values. All the materials were sterilized to avoid any sort of contamination. Bacterial identification in the flesh and skin of fish will be done using media like Nutrient Agar. For the determination of total viable bacterial count, these media can be used.

Culturing of Bacteria

In a separate petri dish, samples were taken from the flesh and skin of the fish. A solid gel-like consistency of culture media was attained by growing 20ml of culture media in petri dishes followed by leaving it for some time. Dissection of the fish gut is done using a sterilized apparatus and the sample taken was transferred to a 9% saline solution contains in a flask. Shake well until homogenized. Serial dilutions were made and 10 microliters of suspension were placed on culture media (solidified) and inoculated in an incubator at 37°C. After incubation, the bacterial colonies were seen after 24 hours that were studied visually. For the identification/characterization of the staining property of flesh and skin microbes. Gram staining was performed. An average of three was considered an accurate count in standard lab analysis. So, three petri dishes were prepared with agar media spreading uniformly in petri plates using a sterilized rod. The total bacterial count can be measured using the formula:

Total viable count = Average number of colonies \times Dilution factor

Statistical and Graphical analyses

At the end of the microbial analyses, the obtained data was subjected to graphical analyses. In graphical analysis MINITAB software was used for comparison of microbial count of salted, frozen and marketed fish samples.

RESULTS

The current experiment purpose was to compare the microbial quality of frozen and salted fish samples collected from District Faisalabad. The analysis of experiment was conducted on December 20, 2023. The results were showed that microbial count of salted and frozen fish samples was less then that marketed fish samples.

Graph 1: Microbial count of sardine salted, frozen and marketed samples

Graph 2: Microbial count of Rohu salted, frozen and marketed samples.

Graph: 3 Microbial count of Tuna salted, frozen and marketed fish samples.

Graph: 4 Microbial count of Rohu,Sardine and Tuna salted frozen and marketed fish samples.

DISCUSSION

The current experiment was executed to conduct the microbial evaluation of frozen and salted fish samples collected from district Faisalabad. The primary aim was

to evaluate the microbial composition of frozen and salted fish samples. Flesh and skin samples were used for microbiological evaluation.

Graph 1 depicted that the microbial count of the marketed Sardine flesh sample was 191 % as compared to salted and frozen Sardine flesh and skin samples. The microbial count of salted and frozen Sardine samples was 0 as compared to marketed samples.

Graph 2 depicted that the microbial count of the marketed Rohu flesh and skin samples was 4 and 8 % respectively as compared to salted and frozen Rohu flesh and skin samples. The microbial count of salted and frozen Rohu samples was 0 as compared to marketed samples.

Graph 3 depicted the microbial count of the marketed Tuna flesh samples was 26 % as compared to salted and frozen samples. The microbial count of salted and frozen Tuna samples was 0 as compared to marketed samples.

Graph 4 revealed the comparison of microbial count of marketed Rohu, Sardine and Tuna samples as compared to salted and frozen Rohu, Sardine and Tuna samples.

The present study focus on understanding the microbial status of the flesh and skin of fish with different stains and nutrient media. The number and variety of microbes associated with fish are influenced by the geographical place, the season, and the harvest procedure. Frozen Rohu, salted Sardines were taken from Metro mall, Intiaz Super Market and Bambino Departmental Store. Samples were taken from the flesh and skin.

Fishes are more perishable than other protein foods and thus more prone to bacterial contamination than salted and frozen fish. Similar results were investigated in fresh fish by Adebayo *et al.*, 2012 and Also Mohhdaly *et al.*, 2021 stated that salting could be used to obtain a product which maintains almost all its nutritional characteristics with a longer shelf life.

Freezing preserves food for extended periods because it prevents the growth of microorganisms that cause both food spoilage and foodborne illness. Similar results were investigated in Rohu by Afrin *et al.*, 2021 who stated that Reducing storage temperature reduces the number and types of micro-organisms able to grow and should reduce the growth rate of those that are able to grow.

Like other seafood products, Tuna is highly perishable and sensitive to microbial spoilage. Its consumption, whether fresh or canned can lead to severe food poisoning due to the activity of specific microorganisms, including histamine producing bacteria. Similar results reported in tuna by Valdenegro *et al.*, 2013. Also Kapetanović *et al.*, 2017 stated that marketed Tuna skin has greater microbes than salted and frozen Tuna fish because microorganisms may come from the environment and are considered to be naturally present in fresh fish.

CONCLUSION

Thus, it was concluded that flesh fish skin and flesh contained greater microbes than salted and frozen fish. But fresh fish meat is more perishable than other protein foods irrespective of the fact that it is more prone to bacterial contamination as compared to salted and frozen fish meat.

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